

THE ROLE OF SOCIAL SCIENCES IN THE FORMATION OF A LAWYER'S PERSONALITY

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Abstract: *The article discusses the importance of public speaking skills, time management, initiative, creativity, creativity and logical thinking in the work of a lawyer. In particular, students studying in the specialty of jurisprudence, in such areas as state, criminal, civil, labor, environmental law, acquire knowledge about the laws, regulations relating to these areas, as well as when and how to apply them. This knowledge is called "hard skills" in world pedagogy – hard, stable skills. In the same world pedagogy as in the world's leading law schools, there is a set of knowledge called "soft skills" – soft, mobile skills. This knowledge and skills can be mastered only with the help of social sciences, or rather, academic subjects arising from the combination, complementarity of specialties and social sciences.*

Keywords: *Lawyer, lawyer's activity, oratory, time management, initiative, creativity, creative approach, logical thinking.*

Introduction

Guaranteed legal provision of society, exclusively and exclusively legal regulation of relations between citizens and the state are the most important condition, if I may say so, a decisive indicator of the formation of a truly democratic system in our country. The comprehensive development of the most advanced countries of the world is based on strict observance of this rule, turning it into the norm of everyday life.

In the accelerated formation of these rules and regulations, turning them into an integral part of our daily life – universally recognized and respected skills, the role of lawyers – creators, implementers, supervisors of how these rules and regulations work is invaluable. (We use the word "unsurpassed" not just to add luster to the statement, but also in its original meaning, since it is necessary and makes sense to use it here. After all, "incomparable" means "incomparable", and in solving the issues and problems we are talking about, it is really impossible to find another social

stratum that could replace lawyers, and if “found”, then compare their weight!).

Thus, in this sense, we can say that the formation of the country's lawyers as a person, as a conscious person, fully responsible for himself, is crucial for strengthening citizens' confidence in the law, social justice, and, therefore, in the reality of the idea of building a democratic state based on the rule of law. This just and responsible person can never be put on his feet and integrated into society without social sciences, their influence and support [1].

Without denying the partial significance and role of exact and natural sciences, subjects of pure specialty in mastering certain professions, it should be said that they are more and more aimed at the formation and development of intelligence, professional concepts and skills of a human child. In particular, students studying in the specialty of jurisprudence, in such areas as state, criminal, civil, labor, environmental law, acquire knowledge about the laws, regulations relating to these areas, as well as when and how to apply them. This knowledge is called “hard skills” in world pedagogy – hard, stable skills. In the same world pedagogy as in the world's leading law schools, there is a set of knowledge called “soft skills” – soft, mobile skills. This knowledge and skills can be mastered only with the help of social sciences, or rather, academic subjects arising from the combination, complementarity of specialties and social sciences.

The Main Findings and Results

In particular, the syllabus (curriculum) of the module “Legal skills and methodology” (“Legal skills and methodology”), which has been taught at Tashkent State Law University for three years, contains the following topics: “Initiative in the activity of a lawyer, creativity and a creative approach to business”, “Personal development plan of a lawyer”, “Time management: methods of effective time management in school and at work”, “Lawyer's speech culture”, “The role of logically correct thinking and legal justification in the lawyer's activities”, “Legal ethics and professional responsibility”, “Lawyer, professional ethics of employees of investigative and prosecutor's offices and judges”, etc.

As you can see, most of the questions listed above fall outside the scope of specialized disciplines. Taking into account that they are very helpful in the proper formation of personality, psychology, qualifications and skills of a modern lawyer. Without them, this man, sajiya, skills and abilities are either too alien, or if he goes too far, he will find himself in a difficult position.

Suppose that the majority of lawyers who carry out activities in any of the areas of the sphere, the presence of initiative, the ability to creatively and deeply critically approach problems leads to a quick, without excessive bureaucratic red tape, and most importantly – a fair solution of issues that need to be addressed? It is then that the methods of office work remaining from *dakkiyun* – paperwork, bureaucracy, a one-sided approach to all issues and, as a result, the imposition of completely incorrect, unfair sentences - will be eliminated faster in law offices [2, 3, 6, 8].

And while the future lawyer will be taught to formulate a personal development plan correctly, starting from the first days of his student life – just for the sake of a diploma, “what if I could finish my studies, it would be a fat sentence”, in the form of thinking and self-determination (only my own destiny?!) - gives hope to change a risky reality, such as an indifferent, abstract attitude to one's future.

In the end (our human child!) let's think about one thing: in the spring – at a time when mutton has become cheaper, the person who bought four lambs that came out of milk will also have a plan, a well-thought-out goal. In such circumstances, how can a future lawyer – in the fate of the state and society, as we noted above, not have a clear plan for the continuous development of his personality as a master of an extremely important role profession? And as a result of this, the question arises: how to give a person who does not develop a personality, does not come to life for what, why he lives and what his people, society expect from him, and who does not see accordingly, the right to relate to the fate of others, if he is a judge, you can believe in *in chuun*..

Among the topics of the module was the question “lawyer's speech culture”. After all, the inability of many lawyers who give interviews on a TV channel or give speeches at a seminar where hundreds of listeners gather, to speak out not on paper, to say something simple related to their profession as a person, to say a lot, to be frank, indicates serious shortcomings in the intellectual level - knowledge, professional level, worldview, the identity of these “specialists” [4, 5, 20, 24].

In order not to get into such ugly situations tomorrow, students:

what sentence should be pronounced to whom, when, how and in what quantity;

in this case, it should be borne in mind that in the speaking voice, facial expressions, gestures, clothes - in the head;

during his speech, the great actor Shukur Burkhonov, in short, will master the questions about what other methods and techniques he prefers to use to “remember the cough of even a blue person sitting in the hall”...

It is no coincidence that among the topics of the module is the question “the role of logically correct thinking and legal justification in the activities of a lawyer”. In the modern world, where globalization and the scale of information are incredibly expanding, the power of information pressure requires each of us to protect ourselves from this information, to consider it on the basis of a critical and creative approach, rather than direct perception, highlighting important and useful information through logical thinking [7, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14]. And this happens in the process of logical thinking.

Thinking is a process of cognitive activity of a person characterized by a direct and generalized reflection of reality [14, 16, 17, 18]. Logical thinking is one of the highest stages of thinking, expressing the connection of thoughts on the basis of sequence, sequence and embodying an important aspect of the creative activity of the individual [21]. Thus, logical thinking refers to thinking in such a way that the existence, reality or impressions that a person sees, hears, knows, feels and perceives are understandable to others [22]. Logic is a process of thinking that follows the laws of thinking in written and oral speech [23]. In this process, the laws of contradiction, contradiction, exclusion and sufficient reason are harmoniously manifested. Based on the laws of logic, we achieve a clear, consistent, conflict-free and, most importantly, justification of our thoughts.

Conclusion

We can quote in detail similar interpretations with respect to each remaining topic in the module, of course. But we think it's better to leave this creative, thought-fueling work to our esteemed readers themselves.

In conclusion, let's say that no matter how globalized the world is, how technocratic life is, the soul, heart, and human nature of a human child will crave the same human relationships, will constantly try to preserve human values. Consequently, since man is a social being, his means of subsistence and livelihood cannot be separated from society – community. Only a person who has profoundly mastered the knowledge and skills contained in the social sciences about the life of this society can contribute to ensuring that the society to which he belongs is fair, well-intentioned and, ultimately, happy.

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